

Patriarchy, Social Control, and Feminism in Meitei Society

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Abstract

The Meitei society in Manipur is steeped in traditions and cultural mores. While some are extremely enriching, some are dubiously challenging or serve to undermine the agency of a woman. These exercise immense social control over the society and lay the context as well as define and confine hierarchical gender relations. Hence, a reflexive understanding of this complex relationship is vital towards understanding gender dynamics in this small but very vibrant society. This paper provides an auto-ethnographic insight interspersed and strengthened with secondary literature review. The prevailing discourse or narratives relating to women of Meitei society has been a major impetus in the nurturance of this account and reflexivity. The body of the woman, controlled by the patriarchs and many times by the older matriarchs too, are contextualized through their customary rites and rituals such as during matrimony, menstruation, and their participation in political activism. The garment adorned by Meitei women on the lower halves of their bodies, namely, the *Phanek*, is also taken as a significant site for study in this paper.

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Culture then acts to work upon them to exert social control. This paper seeks to highlight the conflict between grand narratives that project Meitei women as extremely liberated and empowered vis-à-vis metanarratives that challenge these notions. The much eulogized women's movement in Manipur is missing the skeleton in the closet. Women, in general, thus seem to be the never mended sole on men's shoes.

Keywords: *Culture, Meitei, Meira Paibis, Menstruation, Woman's Attire, Woman's Body*

Introduction

Social control theory was developed by Travis Hirschi in 1969. It is also known as the social bond theory. Under social control theory, individuals break the law due to a breakdown with their societal bond. Sociologists define social control as the way that the norms, rules, laws, and structures of society regulate human behavior. It is understood as the process whereby society seeks to ensure conformity to the dominant values and norms in that society. It refers to the system of devices whereby society brings its members into conformity with the accepted standards of behaviour. Methods of social control could either be formal or informal. Law is a formal method of social control while informal methods include ostracism, ridicule, gossip, and censure.

Control here refers to the authority and power to direct, command, and restrain women and of being able to take unilateral decisions regarding their lives. Ideology and social beliefs which get channelized as cultural or societal norms, are used to exercise control over resources and women's actions, bodies, and sexuality. Societal apparatuses such as the "distribution of resources, or entitlements such as education, food, property; organisation of space, work, and time; rules of avoidance and respect; socialisation patterns; and in general, the denial of choices and opportunities to develop self-worth" (Dube 8) are significant determinants of social control. This paper will dwell upon these from the gender perspective.

Meitei Women and Political Activism

It is imperative to understand the society we are observing to comment upon how social control operationalises itself. The *Meiteis* also known as *Meeteis*, are the predominant ethnic group of Manipur, a small state in the Northeast region of India. They are largely a traditional and orthodox society in terms of its various societal practices such as marriages, childbirths, deaths, and such other social conventions. Moreover, there is a huge dichotomy between the public, (which refers mostly to the state), and the private spheres of life. The public sphere is actually political culture. Margaret R. Somers had suggested that ‘cultural’ as a concept refers more to what is ‘naturalized’ than to what is recognizably cultural (114). When we examine the conceptual network and historical sociology of concept formation, these emerge as strong truths. Hence, the epistemological foundations of any concept remain paramount in deconstructing it.

The jewel in the crown of the Meitei women’s movement has indeed been the historic *Nupi Laan* (women’s war). The first *Nupi Laan* broke out in 1904 in the erstwhile kingdom of Manipur, which almost coincided with the nationalist struggle that was gaining a foothold in India. It served as a major impetus to push women into the public sphere. The partition of Bengal in 1905 and the Swadeshi movements elsewhere in India was beginning to raise feminist consciousness. Women were beginning to enter the fray for their own rights as well. Many women’s organizations also took birth and by the 1930s, the demand even grew for legislative reforms to protect the rights of women. This social and political climate could perhaps have also served as a backdrop to the *Nupi Laan* movement. However, till date, the women’s movements in Manipur occupies a paradoxical place as it has continued to steer itself away from all the issues that concern women’s rights specifically. It has been occupying centerstage only in macro issues that are in the domain of the public sphere. The micro issues that pertain to the private sphere are ignored and hence an undue dichotomy is created and perpetuated.

The discourse surrounding Meitei women has been woven around grand narratives that eulogize their bravados, beginning with the tempestuous *Nupi Laan*, which has oft-been plated up to hark

Meitei society to its apparently women-centric society. Ningombam Rojibala too questions whether the *Nupi Laan* movements are justified in being referred to as women's movements as they were focused on the political problem of the time rather than any women's issue in particular (5). Such historical accounts of yore, and those in contemporary times like that of the Kangla fort protest, that of Irom Sharmila against the Armed Forces Special Powers Act (AFSPA), 1958, have acted to intensify the image of a bold and publicly active Meitei woman. Paromita Chakravarti writes that the naked protest at the Kangla fort, especially, has underlined how women can challenge the state, and gender can become the fulcrum of a larger peacebuilding movement in strife-torn Manipur (53-56). She also invokes the tradition of women's relationship with the larger history and polity of Manipur, which relates to the historic *Nupi Laan* movements (51). However, what is pertinent is, does feminist activism in Manipur then get confined only to public or political issues that concern peacebuilding? What kind of feminism then is required to tackle the agonies that lie within the private spheres and the domains of domesticity?

Very recently, the contested roles of the *Meira Paibis* (torch bearers) during the ethnic carnage that has unsettled Manipur since May 3, 2023, have prompted society watchers to perceive Meitei society as one replete with soft feminism, to say the least. They have been engaged in a fiery manner, almost to the extent of allowing themselves to be weaponized as a tool in this entire narrative. The thriving *Ima* market adds on to the glorious aura and the relatively pseudo-notion of a society that frees its women to pursue their choices. The irony lies in the fact that such glorification and deification veiled the sufferings and agonies of the Meitei women in their daily lives. The economic encumbrances that challenge the women to participate in the economic activities of the *Ima* market is looked at through myopic lenses. Only their will to participate is exalted but not the compulsions in their family lives, owing to economic needs. Hence, the pressures of patriarchy are overlooked, which visibly distorts the understanding of gender relations in Meitei society. Out of multiple social realities, those charting the discourse steered the narratives to present the subject of study as per their own value choices. Thus, challenging the ideal type is an outcome of post-modernism. The multiple perspectives and multiple realities

that exist, must produce multiple knowledge. However, the fact remains that there are also multiple standpoints that women would take, wherein feminists would be left gasping; as several women would concur that her ideal place is the home and the hearth. Herein lies the paradox. The challenge is therefore to adopt unconventional methodologies that would unearth oppressive social structures and power inequities in the research process that can propagate strong feminist concerns and overthrow patriarchy.

Customary Traditions, Societal Norms and Patriarchy

Duncan McDuie-Ra writes about 'softer patriarchy' in the Northeast region of India. In some ways, such a subtle expression perhaps captures the gender relations in this region as women in this region are viewed as more empowered and egalitarian in their relations with men. It is perceived that the practice of 'Christianity, indigenous faiths, less rigid forms of Hinduism' (120) and being less bounded by conservative traditions have served to create this opinion. Another pointer he adds is about the 'visibility' of women, where they move around unchaperoned by a male or any other relative. The congregation of women in large numbers in public places, such as the *Ima* market, and the engagement in all instances by the *Meira Paibis*, can tell a completely different story and impress upon the uninitiated 'outsider' in a totally different way about gender dynamics in Meitei society. However, these truths remain on the surface as Meitei society grapples with a host of gender-based challenges. McDuie-Ra also writes about how representation of women in politics in the Northeast is the lowest in India. He also asserts that patriarchy in the region is getting stronger as there is rapid onset of socio-economic change (122).

McDuie-Ra brings to the fore a very pertinent aspect about the attitudes of men and women towards violence against women. In a survey conducted by the National Family Health Survey, 2009, he notes the responses of men and women justifying wife beating from a list of reasons provided. They ranged from going out without informing, neglecting the house or children, argumentative, saying no to sex, not cooking well, suspicion of promiscuity, disrespect for in-laws. He highlights an alarming number of 89.7% of women and 85% of men from Manipur who agreed with at least one of the

reasons (123). These ring ominous alarm bells about the gender dynamics in the state.

There are a wide range of culturally induced norms that prevail in any society and they determine what is acceptable or not. These serve to promote the long-standing reign of patriarchy. Both the men and women are the social actors of interest and analysis. Social reality is sought to be understood through their web of interactions that has created these norms and traditions that are riddled with patriarchal fervour. The dominant patriarchal culture thus creates and presents a distorted worldview, which gains legitimacy through societal and cultural constructs. Below are enlisted a few of the unique prevalences in Meitei society that are not always obvious to the routine eye, but are deeply embedded in it. These have been informed by feminist insights, feminist analysis, and feminist research.

Son Preference

Varied customs surround Meitei society, just like in any other society. Preference for begetting a son is one such custom. These customary indicators of patriarchy in many covert and overt ways thus prevail in Meitei society. A mother is bestowed a much higher status if she begets a son as first-born. It confers a benign prestige as she thus has ensured the continuity of the male lineage by fulfilling her biological responsibilities in a manner that society prefers. The clan is rest assured of its steadiness of existence. On the other hand, the woman who could not beget a son, first-born or otherwise, has to undergo the anxieties and private agonies of fall of stature, which in many ways remain very covert, as society doesn't deem it necessary to be overlooked. Rather, emotional wounds are accorded via certain other actions and words by linking it with cultural do's and don't's. Many a times, the in-laws prefer to reside with the daughter-in-law's family who has begotten a son. In a traditional society, these markers exhibit undue emotional angst and pressure upon the young daughter-in-law.

Son preference is not merely an expression of the society. Owing to the indoctrination and acculturation of the norms of a patriarchal society, the woman herself often desires for a son. Societal conditioning and the norms that govern their conduct have

managed to manufacture and instill within the women a sense of achievement based upon the procreation of a male progeny. Various societal and cultural sanctions disfavour women who do not beget a son. They are discreet and covert but are laden with societal weightage that hangs very heavily on the shoulders of the Meitei women. Thus, not only is the burden of biological reproduction a huge responsibility upon the women. Practices such as these springing from patriarchy, where hierarchy accorded to women upon begetting a male heir or not, is a kind of a militant patriarchy. These, are unlike what people from the outside prefer to see as soft patriarchy.

Weber had propounded that social reality is constructed via cultural values and practices. Shalini Shah writes about how patriarchal cultures tend to exercise social control over the women. Throughout history, they harboured and advocated the ideas that the female body needed to be controlled so that her reproductive powers were channelized towards a male progeny, hence ensuring the blood line goes on undisturbed (36). The *Manusmriti* accords unequivocal power to the male seed and the womb as a mere resting place. It was upon her to perform her duty to ensure that a son is begotten so that the household benefits economically (33).

Unpaid Household Labour

Meitei society is laden with some unequal juxtapositions of household responsibilities between the two genders. Khundrakpam and Sarmah also concur that women are expected to do almost all of it and a man who helps her is seemingly ridiculed by the society (102674). These gender role expectations cannot be shaken off despite her own engagements as a “working woman”. Such encumbrances weigh heavily upon her just like in any other patriarchal society. A host of domestic responsibilities, written off as not amounting to work, owing to the lack of economic revenues being generated from it, tie her down. These certainly do not seem to champion women’s rights and gender equality. Such situations bring about a range of impediments on the daily lives of the Meitei woman. The perception of the ideal Meitei woman that is ingrained in the subconscious as well as conscious of Meitei society, makes the lives of these women even more complex.

When Nancy Hartsock talks about the sexual division of labour, it hints at how women's oppression is a political endeavour. Hence, reflecting over these routine sounding discussions of household labour, can definitely have the effect of raising consciousness amongst the women (234). The social and economic value of women's work in the home has been a problem that has perplexed social and political scientists, economists, and feminists alike. The "wages for housework" somehow failed to rattle mainstream discourse as it was never taken seriously by economists. Hence, it remains a beleagueringly romanticised phenomenon for the women who bear the major burden of 'actually' running the family, unpaid and unprotected with any kind of social security, except for the very poor, who may have access to some Government schemes (Hirschmann 199). Thus, it remains a tragic irony that women's rights at the work place or in the public sphere has not translated into any kind of equality in the very vital private sphere or the family.

Meanwhile, Rai notably points out that the patriarchal sexual division of labour began to be challenged as women gained education and entered the public sphere. They became more opinionated and would not settle for silence always (58). This began to unsettle the well ensconced sexual division of labour and hence patriarchy had to look for new ways and means to maintain the sexual status quo. Thus, it can be inferred that a range of social control measures were woven into the Meitei society to keep her in place.

Matrimony and its Rites of Passage

Besides my own first-hand observations, other scholars (Khundrakpam and Sarmah 102674) too have observed and noted that the harbinger of marital alliances, referred to as the *Jatra-pubi*, is a very sought-after position in Meitei matrimonial customary rites and rituals. It is she who is looked at as the one who will initiate the journey into holy matrimony for the newlyweds, and hence assumes a lot of prestige and recognition. The socially and customarily marked, albeit unwritten criteria for the *jatra-pubi*, should be an ideal Meitei woman. Having a son as firstborn is one of the special

characteristics she must possess. A mother who does not qualify this, remains ineligible for even mere consideration.

Another significant change that is sweeping Meitei society in the realm of marriage is regarding the *awunpot* (wedding gifts) system. Till today, many Meiteis boast of a dowry-free society. But this narrative holds no water as such a practice of bestowing elaborate wedding gifts have become essential. Society watchers are continuously assessing and evaluating one's net worth based upon the scale of such *awunpot*. Reports of bride torture in the wake of insufficient *awunpot* have slowly but gradually beset Meitei society. Even if there has been no clear violence, the disdain or the ridicule expressed in the absence of such gifts are sufficient to confirm the necessity of such marital practices in Meitei society. Hence it would be a systemic falsehood to claim that the evils of the dowry system are non-prevalent (Khundrakpam and Sarmah 102674).

The Impure Woman

Notions of purity and impurity abound in every society in different forms and different intensities. However, these notions are always more encumbering on a woman. Khundrakpam and Sarmah document that in Manipur, an unmarried Meitei maiden post-puberty is referred to as a *leishabi* (literally meaning “one that resembles a budding flower”) until her marriage. Menstruation is referred to as *amangba* (impure) or *masa sengdaba* (unclean body) in Meitei culture; and there is no non-misogynist term that describes it other than these or similar words. A menstruating woman is not allowed to enter the kitchen in Meitei culture and anything she touches is an act of *mangtbokpa* (defilement). She is not allowed to enter the room of the *Sanamabi* (traditional deity of the Meitei home) or offer prayers to any deity including the Tului deity that is placed at the courtyard. On non-menstruating days, she is expected to perform all these duties. Defiled clothes worn during menstruation must not be brought out in public, especially under male scrutiny. Such practices are sustained through a long process of familial and social conditioning wherein the elders of the family, especially women, play an important role (Khundrakpam and Sarmah 102674). Menstruating days have been considered as equivalent to impure, necessitating the woman to almost be an outcast during those few

days. The older matriarchs ensure that no line of control is trespassed by the menstruating young woman. Her roles and responsibilities within the household are also under the watchful gaze of these older women, especially the mother-in-law. Established norms and taboos confine the young woman as to what she can wear, when could she return home, who could she go out with, and what could be her typical engagements. All these go on to carve that niche of an “ideal Meitei woman”. A marked distance is to be maintained from the men of the family, to delineate gender roles. The concept of what is forbidden and what is not amongst the women, are almost scripted and inscribed from the very early childhood days, in their minds, which goes on to eulogize an ideal Meitei woman. Such taboos associated with menstruation have been prevalent in many societies, and have been documented in early extant literature.

A range of meanings can be inferred about existing gender relations and the gender structure of the society through such practices. Mitoo Das opines that gendered rituals and taboos impinging upon purity and pollution create a visibly gendered society. Bordering between something as personal as hygiene and something very societal like religious rites and rituals, the practice of purity and pollution during menstruation can confer very strong but covert power relations between the two genders. She highlights how such pollutions during menstruation and during delivery are involuntary and temporal, and men find the women during such times “unusable” (Das). Such representations of purity and impurity get so ordained, that they acquire strong symbolic meanings and get institutionalized, thus gaining total social acceptability. Jyoti Puri (1999) talks about containing woman’s power and her intrinsic inferiority (56) that can be inferred through such practices. Dumont (1988) highlights how Hinduism concurs that menstruation is a polluting agent. In various Indian societies, a ritual is conducted at the onset of menarche. These acquire deeply engaging meanings as it announces the biological role of the woman, yet her subordinate status, where she needs to be reined in (qtd. in Das 31). Therefore, such social mechanisms in Meitei society also serves to imbue the women about the gendered power relations, and her lack of agency. Such a consciousness only serves to distort the emancipatory ideals of the Meitei woman.

The Phanek and its Embodiments

In Meitei society, the *Phanek* is paradoxical in meaning and stature. It is deeply venerated as a symbol that idealizes the strength and potentialities that are associated with the identity of an ideal Meitei woman. The garment is accorded a stature that defies motherhood, and creates the imagery of a protector. Its worthiness and being sacrosanct is extolled by the practice of wearing a piece of the *phanek* as a talisman, considered to ward off all evil. From the days of yore, there have been practices of according it near cosmic powers, where chants of not urinating in the lap of nature, but in one's mother's lap, naturally guarded by a *phanek*, before urinating in the dark, unknown places has been in practice. It is believed that one could be protected from any kind of evil spells. Another instance of the prowess of the *phanek* is when it is used in preparing the local rice beer. An old worn out *phanek* is used to cover it up as it is believed to impart magical powers that will lure the customers to long to have even more.

The *phanek* thus seeks to represent and symbolize femininity and all the majestic and sovereign powers it could bring. Motherhood which is so revered, especially in Indian society, is closely associated with this garment and all the strength it can entail or embody. However, such sacredness to this mystic garment is viewed through the lens of the new discourses on women. A woman's attire to depict femininity is one of those few privileges that a 'benevolent' patriarchy has endowed upon the feminine. But the flip side is that such an accordance of femininity and the associated roles of motherhood has also entailed the additional encumbrances of child rearing and nurturance. Thus, the patriarchal forces get to define and delineate where must femininity begin and end; and what must it entail.

Starkly contrasting observations and practices prevail regarding this 'honourable' garment that defies the power of the feminine. It is prohibited to be washed with other clothes, especially those worn by the menfolk. Nor must it be dried with other clothes in the open courtyard as it is considered ominous of forebodings that can spell ill luck, especially when a male member of the household is headed out for work. Men also must not handle the garment under any circumstances. This is in sharp contrast to other

parts of India where men also weave sarees and work as salespersons in the stores, many times even draping it upon themselves to induce increased sales. Men in Meitei society, on the contrary, are wary that if they even touch a *phanek*, they would be ridiculed. It is also a belief in Meitei society that if we hit someone with a *phanek*, it is extremely humiliating and the intention is also thus.

The agency of a woman, therefore, is always in question, beginning with social control over the very piece of clothing that adorns her. Such social control steeped in patriarchy, have taken on the private lives of Meitei women. It has permeated into Meitei society and has occupied a place that has been normatively embedded into acceptable and expected societal practices. Thus, the personal has indeed become political. This falls along the ideas of Sylvia Walby wherein private patriarchies have paved the ways for public patriarchy (178). These spell doom for gender equality. Patriarchal civil society (Pateman 35) is another burgeoning aspect observed in Meitei society, which propels the continuity of such rigid dichotomies of gender.

Controlling Woman's Attire Through the Male Gaze

There had been diktats propelled by patriarchal civil society groups comprising of student leaders and insurgent groups propagating the *phanek* as compulsory wear for school going girls beginning from 12 to 13 years of age (Thokchom par. 2). This can be observed as coinciding with the onset of puberty and menarche. It was aimed at guarding the female 'honour' via the *phanek*, and to exercise social control over the female body. Patriarchal positioning of an ideal woman as one who should be chaste and within the ambit of the perceptions of how femininity must be preserved by the dominant patriarchy were responsible for this change in attire. The construction of femininity is thus very 'complex, contradictory, and continuous' (Dube).

Saurav Kumar Rai contextualizes the perverted misogyny in our society by discussing about the Nirbhaya incident, wherein the onus and blame of the lustful male gaze is passed on to the woman for failing to cover her body well, and hence failing to protect herself. In 2012, Banwari Lal Singhal, an MLA from Rajasthan, too invoked the 'safety' of women, and wished for skirts to be replaced by the *salwar-kameez* as school uniform (49). Rai points out that it

was with the emergence of the middle class in the late nineteenth and early twentieth century that brought women's clothing to the fore, as points of debate. Social reforms took birth, necessitated by the patriarchal society and its oppressive ways. Thus, controlling the attire, mobility, and public life access was a tool to further the patriarchy. It based itself on the threat of a looming and lurking male gaze and its consequences, that in turn could bring dishonour and disrepute to the woman's family. The gaze is a powerful social instrument as it can unnerve a person and create undue anxiety and even shame. Rai has used Jacques Lacan's concept of the gaze to illustrate and analyze how lust and lechery can invoke powerful feelings unto the male and completely disempower and almost destroy the confidence of the female, who is thus being subjected to the sexually charged male gaze (Rai 50). Thus, the male gaze itself once again becomes a means of social control over women in a patriarchal social structure.

Meitei Women, Nationhood, and the Gender Discourse

The Meitei women have not only been historically touted as heroic in terms of the *Nupi Laan*. Their bravadoes have been sung and fortified in the quest of an anti-assimilation with the political ethos of India, thus legitimizing their resistance. This was observed strongly during the resistance against the AFSPA, 1958, which had been eventually revoked from most of the valley areas of Manipur. What is noteworthy is that every woman participating in any resistant group adorns the *phanek*. It is accorded a pride of place alluding a sense of bravery to the Meitei women, whose identification stands tall, courtesy the *phanek*. Thus, the woman's body and her feminine self is projected as a site of resistance to the onslaught of the normativity of western or Indian attire. Such a co-option of the women of Meitei society, wherein their homogenization with the larger nation-state of India is resisted and prevented is described as a new patriarchy.

It is also noteworthy that when the *Meira Paibis* engage in such public participatory processes, only the *phanek* is to be worn by each Meitei woman. It is like an unwritten code. This is yet another instance of social control where the Meitei identity of the woman is to be solidified through her outfit. The Association of Meiteis in the

Americas (AMA) organized peace demonstrations in San Francisco, California, regarding the ongoing ethnic conflict in Manipur. All the women protestors wore the *pungou phanek*. This is of a specific peach colour, that is worn by Meitei women during mourning. But the men wore very routine attire of shirt and pants (IFP). Thus, the onus apparently falls upon women to be the vanguards of society, whenever it is in turmoil. Besides, on all occasions of social rites and rituals, the *phanek* is worn by Meitei women.

In a neoliberal and post-modern era, the ‘new-age woman’ is set to counter these germane perspectives as she starts questioning ownership of her body and her conduct. The other pertinent question is the perception and receptivity of the Meitei women towards such diktats. New discourse, and especially feminist studies on Meitei society reveal that social and economic positioning of the women determine their perceptions. The legitimization of archaic and irrational customs and traditions such as menstrual impurity; according pride of place to those who beget a son as first-born; and the contested status of the *phanek* are being deeply analyzed in a neoliberal and post-modern world. However, it is to be noted that the *Meira Paibis* (torch bearing women), have not engaged themselves towards addressing women’s rights or any issues on gender equality. They have confined themselves to public issues of the state as could be seen through their active participation in the wake of the recent ethnic upheaval that has shaken Manipur since May 3, 2023. Other instances have been to call for the revocation of the AFSPA, 1958, or to counter economic blockades, or such other politically charged issues of the state. Amidst the din of all these, however, from within Meitei society itself, especially younger and educated women, questions are arising as to why they shy away from issues that concerns women’s rights and gender equality.

The much-acclaimed *Ima* market and the historical *Nupi laan* have been deified and invoked to typify the image of an empowered Meitei woman. Hence it is essential to deconstruct and renavigate through the terrain of gender discourse in Meitei society. New narratives prefer to remap these imageries of the profoundly legendary-like status accorded to women. Questions arise that if these historical incidents have indeed been a women’s movement, how is it that the rights of women have never found a mention? Was it ever a women’s movement? Was it even a women-led movement?

These are questions rattling the post-modern feminist scholars, in particular.

Desexualization of the Meitei Women in Meitei Society

Meitei society is replete with edginess when it has to deal with sexuality. The world renowned *Raas Lila* dance depicting love between Lord Krishna and Radha has also been desexualized in a way, in terms of performance, where both the roles are enacted by women. The traditional *Shumaang Leela* (Courtyard Performance) in Meitei society, which also occupies a pride of place is again contrastingly enacted only by men where women's roles are taken on with equal fervour by *Nupi Shaabis* (acting like a woman). This is applicable for the men's theatre groups. The women's theatre groups in turn have all the roles played by women. All these practices seemingly point towards an attempt at desexualising the woman. Machunwangliu Kamei notes that in the olden days, the conservative Meitei society did not favour women travelling to distant places with men for such performances. Hence troupes were comprised solely of men, who had to step in to enact women's roles. They had to undergo rigorous training to 'feminise' themselves in terms of appearances and conduct, lest they fail, and the entire performance falters. Such an idealized representation of *Nupi Shaabi* was an outcome of the patriarchal construct. In fact, it is claimed that *Shumang Leela* finds its audience more due to the presence of these *Nupi Shaabis*. It is also highlighted that they are now being replaced by *Nupi Maanbis*, who are transgenders (4).

Furthermore, the very nomenclature of *Ima market*, meaning Mothers' market, to refer to the Khwairamband women's market, is also perceived as an attempt to desexualize womanhood and glamourize motherhood, as the epitome of womanhood. It thus veers towards biological reductionism. The parameters to qualify one as eligible to be a vendor in the market has very deeply telling meanings in understanding gender dynamics and sexuality in Meitei society. One must be married to be eligible to find a place there. Moreover, the *phanek* is preferably worn pulled up over the blouse, thereby covering the breasts. An *innaphee* (a small light or heavy shawl, depending upon the weather) must accompany the entire self-presentation apparel. Hence, femininity must not be allowed to

preclude the display of the subsistence and resistance of women to the penuries of life, however, hard they may be. This is yet another form of social control. Motherhood is the safest garb to be donned by women, albeit endowed upon by a 'benevolent patriarchy'; who claim that they have freed their women from the shackles of economic disempowerment. Therefore, the projection of Meitei women as empowered, independent, and chaste.

The *Meira Paibis* too don similar outfits but mostly with an additional headgear (a piece of cloth covering their heads). Here, also they comprise mostly of married women in the age group of 35 to 60 years and are inextricably linked with the women vendors of the *Ima* market. Such an active participation of all-women brigades in the socio-economic and cultural aspects of public life in any society is indeed quite unprecedented and awe-inspiring. However, what is missing is that they have failed to step into the private sphere of women's lives, where agonizing traumas have been endured by several women. The patriarchy in Meitei society is deeply embedded, oft-hidden, unrecognized, unspoken of, even by these vanguards of civil society. Herein lies the irony. The much adulated and celebrated status of Meitei women thus becomes questionable as she becomes a paradox herself. To fall at the feet of patriarchy, and then make efforts to enthuse the world and convince that Meitei society is a gender equal society, is conflict-ridden and ill-perceived. Perspectives are changing and the neo-liberal Meitei woman is not very comfortable to take this conflict within her stride. The discrepancy between projections of Meitei women having an edge in their society, and the reality of women's lives in the family and other domestic spaces they inhabit are being taken note of.

To be cast in the mould of the mother does not unilaterally absolve Meitei society and both men and women alike from the near fatalistic exaltation of the Meitei women. The irony lies in the fact that it overlooks all her personal sorrows and the very gender unequal world they inhabit. But the micro and mezzo elements at the societal level, namely the family and other domestic relationships have been largely ignored blatantly. Such metanarratives now have begun to dominate the gender discourse on Meitei women and their society. The political culture of the pseudo-image of women worship and their exaltation is thus being challenged.

The Woman's Body

Shalini Shah opines that the woman's body as a site of cultural progression had long been ignored (45). However, historians of gender relations are awakened to the history of the female body as a distinct and vital subject of analysis. Shah also points out how the male body is near devoid of erotica, but rather he is presented more as a divine body within a cosmic framework. The female body on the other hand is represented as weak, subservient, and caught within the paradigms that biology has beset upon them. Motherhood and being the sexual vessel to quench the male thirst, was supposedly her destiny. Her weakness also needed male control and disciplining as her biological body had an inherent and natural inequality. Sherry Ortner thus talks about a nature-culture divide; where the naturally bestowed bodily functions owing to her biology is transcended by men, and a masculine cultural capital established over it. Social anthropologists have thus contributed a lot to feminist interpretations of women's social history. They have also preferred to highlight and eulogize the biological capital that women are endowed with. Procreation and sexual arousal that only a woman's body can provide is celebrated as a unique manifestation of femininity and femaleness. Feminists argue that the body must not be merely seen as a biological site but must be accorded a horde of social and cultural meanings too (Shah 34).

Meanwhile, the woman's body has also been equated with several things profane. Pregnancy results in the loss of youthful appearance. Such dwindling of physical appearance lowers her desirability and hence the decline of her sexual prowess. Shah notes that the menstruating woman being considered a potential pollutant all the time, was likened to a *Sudra*. She ought to be debarred from all sacred space as she is drenched in the blood of Brahmanicide. This inauspiciousness cannot be shaken off even in death, if she is menstruating or has just delivered a baby. Her corpse is denounced as defiled. It was believed that since beauty and youth are temporal and short-lived and hence for a woman to preserve her blessed married state, servility to her husband would help her retain her status. To ensure that not only were they physically controlled but in their minds too, so that they could remain chaste, the *pativrata* ideology was honed into women. As for the widow, she was

'desexualised' by laying out various norms in terms of restrictions on food and clothing. She was controlled so as to make her devoid of any sexual urge and desire (Shah 37). Meitei authors and poets like Soibam HariPriya and Shreema Ningombam have written extensively on how the woman's menstruating body is denounced as a defiler, especially during those tempestuous five days.

In the ascetic renunciation of carnal pleasures, Shah once again illustrates how celibacy connotes different forms of abstinence for the male and the female. To attain *Moksha*, the ancient scriptures only spoke about how the men had to submit themselves to the superiority of the mind (37-39). Contrastingly, for the women, they were viewed as imminent threats to such consciousness raising states of mind. These were the spaces that only the men were to inhabit. Celibacy thus is a celebrated and acquired status of masculinity, whereas females are ascribed celibacy and it is rather thrust upon them due to circumstances. This could be due to the passing away of the husband, or if he is away, or when she is menstruating, or pregnant. Thus, the woman's body is subsumed by patriarchal notions of purity and impurity and the very existential paradigms of women acquire epistemic change.

Decolonising the Woman's Body

Rai discusses how the social reforms for women in India during the nineteenth and twentieth century had its own patriarchal agenda (50). It was fanned by the degraded status of women which had become much fodder for the colonialists, that they began to dwell upon a civilizational critique where women were rated very poorly. Thus, the women's movement was more of a response to the colonial depiction and less of a substantial concern. It was argued that colonial discourse itself was gendered as they critiqued the Indian civilization. Hence social reformers of the time took up the rather upper-class issues related to women such as *Sati*, bride burning, age at consent, and the likes. However, it is also countered that education for women as a consequence of the social reform movement opened up new vistas for them. Reading and writing enabled them to participate in newer domains in the public sphere. This again proved to be a threat to the rising middle class as women began to find their voices. They did not want to overthrow the

patriarchy but to overthrow the colonisers. Accordingly, patriarchy had to be reinvented.

The attire of the Meitei *Meira paibi* woman, that is the *phanek*, more often worn pulled up over the breasts, accompanied by a headwrap can be analogous to the *purdah* or the veil in Indian society. This attire among the Meiteis acquire a symbol of honour and substance, just like the *purdah* is accorded prestige in women-oriented movements. Rai concurs that the *purdah* had intrinsic social status in Indian society and was a determinant of upward social mobility (55). The colonisers however viewed it as an oppressive practice towards women. Hence to counter the civilizational challenge wrought upon by the British, the Hindu social reformers took up the defense of the *purdah* as a measure to thwart the male gaze. Such adoption of the *purdah* was essential when a respectable woman comes to a public place. Thus, this moral dilemma was sought to be resolved by exercising social control over women's attire and their presence in the public sphere. The *phanek*, pulled-up or otherwise simply draped around the waist, therefore connotes that she is aware of the male gaze and hence needs to desexualize herself upon entry to the public sphere as she gets embattled in issues that concern the larger public, equivalent to social reforms. What is pertinent to be reiterated is that the issues being taken up are nowhere closer to those that confine women to her traditional household roles.

Culture and Social Control

When social control is to be analyzed, culture plays a very significant role. It can shape the psychology and political behaviour too. The *Meira Paibis* of Manipur have their genesis as “*Nisha Bandhis*”, engaged in vigilantism against alcoholism and drug abuse around the late 1970s. The safety of the family was no different than the development of the society and the state itself. However, what seems to be missing in the entire oeuvre is that the rights of the woman have been subsumed within the larger perspective of “*Samaj Kanba*” (saving society). No deliberate attempts have yet been made by this apparent women's movement to espouse the cause of gender equality. Hence, such a political or civic culture contributes to the internalization of the beliefs of what is justified or not in a society.

This acquires immense legitimacy over time and acts as a means of social control. It continues to shape the value orientations towards various political processes (Parsons, 1967). Parsons (1967) had put forth that the social system and the political culture determine political outcomes. However, what merits attention is to explore the mélange of value systems that shape political values and political culture. Almond (1980) asserts that political socialization and psychological internalization cannot be the complete answers. It is pointed out that political culture was not merely an outcome of the cultural or political system, but more importantly of the social system. Thus, society is a very significant variable while attempting to understand and interpret any facet of existence.

No discussion on the public sphere could be complete without looking at Habermas (1962-89). His scholarship on the public sphere is one of the most distinguished discourses relating to political culture. He connotes both society and rational discourse within it that can create a free public opinion. Matters of significance must be discussed freely in social life as that is the space in which the public can engage themselves to opine and concur (qtd. in Mah). Thus, Habermas also engages with the Parsonian approach and locates the public sphere not as another aspect of a strict dichotomy but something that links the personal and the political. Harold Mah notes that what is unique in Habermas' observation is that the public sphere is the 'bourgeoisie' space, where matters of 'common concern' were discussed and debated over, based upon reason to arrive at a rational consensus (157). Thus, it served as a structured cultural setting, a spatial domain, wherein multiple social groups try to relate their activities to each other, yet preserves the historical uniqueness of the larger group. This is what can be observed about the *Meira Paibi* movement in Manipur, where political issues, largely dealing with the "other", that is the State, are consensually taken up. These occur in the public sphere and does not rattle the patriarchy as genderised issues are allowed to remain in the private sphere and are hence left out of the ambit of their struggles.

Feminism and the Meitei Women

Chakravarti rues that the feminist scholarship in the northeast has not been studied and analysed much despite the important political and social roles women in the region play (51). What is important

however is to note that violence having marred the region, and especially Manipur, which is the focus of this paper, the women's movement seems rather confined to tackle terrorisation by the state and its allied forces. The efforts of the movement seem to be contained within the macrocosm of the state polity. Such efforts must be definitely hailed because standing tall against any oppressor, more so the state, requires indomitable courage and systemic struggles. Manipur has had a tremendously charged history of women having remained at the forefront of various political movements. However, as outlined above, despite the growing prominence of the *annupot* (dowry) as a requirement, acceptability or blatant nonchalance to domestic violence, and a very limited presence in political office, the Meitei women's movement have been unusually engaged purely in political activism. It is indeed laudable that all these have been despite a very traditional and patriarchal society that they cohabit. Besides the *Nupi Laan*, which took place against the malpractices of British colonialism, the women's movement were yet again instrumental in demanding statehood after the erstwhile kingdom was merged with the Indian union.

The Meitei women's movements have been largely geared towards battling such horrific attacks on the woman's body. The Meitei *Meira Paibi* movement grew out of the *Nasha Bandhi* movement around the 1980s (Chakravarti 53). It was hugely acclaimed and successful as it was primarily geared against alcoholism and drug abuse, which had gripped the state's youth and mostly men. These were wreaking havoc inside the homes and women were bearing the brunt of it. This social problem had become a state menace and the *Nasha Bandhis'* relentless efforts managed to help Manipur declare it an alcohol-free state by law in 1991. However, today, this evolved movement of the *Meira Paibis* appear largely focussed on political activism which has more to do with militarisation and taking on the "other". Hence, the *Meira Paibi* movement lacks the rationale to be justified as a feminist movement. Brara (2002) and Mahanta (2001) also reiterate how they overlook the unequal gender norms, the practice of dowry, polygamy, domestic violence, and local political formations (qtd. in Chakravarti 53). Entrenched in deeply primordial practices within households

that oppress the woman, archaic customary practices that impinge upon a woman's agency, ignoring several other women's issues, they focus only on political and community issues. They thus seem to ignore the problems of the very gender that they are. Steering away from the struggle against patriarchy, which is the core of feminist advocacy and activism provides a lacklustre meaning to the *Meira Paibi* movement in Manipur. A woman's movement it maybe, but certainly it lacks the grain of a feminist movement.

The *Meira Paibi* movement therefore requires to be studied very deeply to unearth their positioning in Meitei society. How do they perceive gender dynamics and the status of women in a very traditional society that shies away from easily discussing issues of sexuality must be examined and analysed. The sexual objectification of Manorama was boldly and radically countered by the *Imas* through their naked protests, where they completely desexualised themselves by invoking motherhood. Through that act, they thwarted the very ideology of rape as a tool for dishonouring women (Chakravarti 55). If such is the strength the women possess to protest against the nation-state, what prevents them from taking up women's personal agonies within the private sphere? The answer perhaps lies in the social control exerted by a deeply traditional and patriarchal society, that would not budge to give way to women's personal aspirations. To make her his equal perhaps bears the foreboding of the end of patriarchy.

Changing Narratives on Women of Meitei society

What is of interest however is that there is significant change seeping into the discourse on Meitei women. These narratives of the ideal Meitei women are being challenged by young women themselves who are now loathe to remain in the shadows. Transformative change is sweeping Meitei society too at some levels, propelled by the winds of change of the women's movements and feminist ideologies sweeping across everywhere. This has been brought in by increased levels of education, an increased participation of women in public life, and above all, economic empowerment which synchronizes very well with social empowerment. New social relationships between the two genders and amongst the men and women separately have been forged.

There is hope for gradual change and improvement, even if not a total end to the patriarchal hegemony as society continues to evolve in unprecedented ways in recent times. What is important is to pick up the threads and weave them so that society provides new ways of functioning and help carve out new relationships. This would create new norms that would get eventually naturalized as gender norms. In fact, a society that transposes the gender ordering and transfuses from one gender to the other, in ways that will help redefine the very concept of gender, is a world one could wish for. Utopian it is, but these will remove gender barriers and hierarchies, that have been at the root of several dystopia in society.

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